

Multiway latent block model for pca tensor decomposition*

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Abstract

A multiway latent block model (WLBM) is proposed for modeling the reduction and the clustering of m-modes tensors via matricial latent variables. BEM-like algorithms allow the parameters inference of the models for tensors with multiple modes. This results into summarizing high-dimensional tensors for pca reduction and visualization in a generic multidimensional setting. The parameterizations are -related or approximated- Canonical Polyadic and Tucker decompositions with dramatically less dimensions than their usual full versions for the latent components.

1 Introduction

When data matrices are large, a clustering can give a quicker access to the data contents than a projection method for reducing the dimensionality of the features. Combining clustering and reduction for the projection of the clusters rather than the projection of the rows or the columns is therefore a promising purpose for data analysis. In visualization, one way to reach this requirement is to show the clusters -plus the rows or columns- on a map after clustering the data by an ad hoc algorithm and reducing the dimensions of the matrix, both separately. For reduction or decomposition/factorization, a related usual way is to construct reduced vector or views of the rows and columns in order to summarize with few dimensions. From a data matrix to a data tensor, one or several modes are added such that the method needs to manage a different algebraic space at three or more modes, otherwise some generative models may be more suitable here.

The family of co-clustering methods makes possible to reveal the hidden association between the rows and the columns of a data table and the modes in a tensor, after that k-means [1] has been improved from intensive researches in clustering. A simultaneous partitioning treats symmetrically the data table or tensor on the contrary to a clustering of just only one mode. Algorithms were introduced earlier in the literature in [2] and [3, 4]. There is also the information-theoretic co-clustering method [5], its generalization [6] for contingency matrices. Other approaches [7] are for instance the general method for prediction [8] or the non negative matricial decompositions [9, 10, 11] for non negative matrice. In [12, 13, 14], the **Latent Block Model** (LBM) and its inference by a variational generalized EM algorithm [15] are introduced. Re-parameterization of these models via latent variables [16, 17, 18] bring new properties to these models for: rows and columns visualizations, dimensions reductions or even tensor decomposition as proposed herein.

Clustering decreases the size of the latent vectors for the reduced views from the modes, this approach is expected to be more scalable than the usual decompositions thanks to the homogeneous blocks summarizing the tensor and dividing the computation burden. Including latent variables for reduction in LBM brings new properties to this model for analysis while complementing recent works to deal with big or huge tensors. Current libraries available as open sources in Python (or R) langage are for instance found in [19, 20, 21, 22, 23] for clustering or decomposition. Note that the vocabury in literature on tensor is diverse with diverse terms like clustering, co-clustering, tri(-)clustering, biclustering, partitioning for groups but also related terms like reordering with coordinates in reduced views of the different modes. Next, distributions are introduced for tensors in order be more general because k-means is known for its non optimality due to its spherical equiprobable clusters only relevant for continuous data despite its good results on some datasets.

*Updated seventh (nearly as previous not published online draft at November 3 2025) version of the draft: closed-form expressions and algorithms are tested for parameters inference in connection with usual decompositions in a new replacing section while experiments are completely updated with images datasets.

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The plan of the paper is as follows. Section 1 is for introducing the problematic. Section 2 is for presenting the foundations for the proposed approach. Section 3 is presents the new multiway latent block model with also the latent variables for the decomposition. Section 4 illustrates the model with the Gaussian cases by presenting three variants, one for co-clustering, one for sparse co-clustering and one for the decomposition or principal component analysis. Section 5 is for the experiments with tensor data for reduction and visualization plus a discussion and comparison with alternative decompositions. Section 6 is the conclusion with the perspectives.

2 Review of foundation models

This section revise several models for reduction or clustering, they are principal component analysis, decomposition/factorization, and tri-clustering. This introduced the basis for the following proposed approach which proceeds via hidden latent variables within a probabilistic model.

Principal component analysis (PCA) for matrix (m=2)

Factorization [24] is a living activity for reducing the dimensionality of matrices. For helping at denoising and clustering, principal component analysis (PCA) [25] aims at the construction of synthetic variables from the original variables or columns of the data matrix. These new variables maximize an explained variance via a projection from the full data cloud to a subspace spanning the columns space. The limited number of new variables or components in the new vectors that replace the (possibly high-dimensional) original one leads to the property of reducing the dimensionality. A new matrix is available with less columns (or rows) than the original matrix. For all these reasons, this method is useful in numerous research areas from an applied statistical analysis to a pre-reduction for another method such that clustering. More formally for $m = 2$ modes, let \mathbf{x} the numerical matrix with n rows d -dimensional \mathbf{x}_i and thus $n \times d$ cells x_{ij} . PCA has several definitions actually in the literature according to diverse purposes. There can be bayesian priors for the reduced vectors, orthogonality and/or positivity/non negativity for the loading matrix, or even a factorization without any other hypothesis. For a matrix with cells $(x_{ij})_{ij}$, the following definitions are widely considered:

- For centered data, PCA is a matricial method [26] which is originally defined as solving for:

$$\hat{R} = \underset{R}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_i \|\mathbf{x}_i - RR^T \mathbf{x}_i\|^2$$

This is equivalent to define as minimizing the reconstruction error of the projected data points into the new subspace, a linear transformation for reducing the space of the columns. Eventually, orthogonality supposes $R^T R = \mathbf{I}$ which often improves the results.

- A factorization [24] is written as follows,

$$(\hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}}, \hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}^{(2)}}) = \underset{\xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}}, \xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(2)}}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i,j} \left(x_{ij} - \xi_i^{\mathbf{x}^{(1)T}} \xi_j^{\mathbf{x}^{(2)}} \right)^2 .$$

A solution is found by regression for solving for $\xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}}$ and keeping $\xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(2)}}$ constant, and similarly for $\xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(2)}}$ when $\xi^{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}}$ is constant. This may be the definition the more convenient for modeling a PCA(-like) method within non Gaussian models, with the distribution function for x_{ij} as depending on these latent vectors or instead cluster related versions in the case of a partitioning as herein.

- In Probabilistic PCA (PPCA [27], it may be written also for non centered data in a cluster:

$$(\hat{\mu}, \hat{W}) = \underset{\mu, W}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_i \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mu - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{y}_i\|^2 .$$

This is the approach used in the probabilistic setting of PCA where this notation is more usual in this family of models. Note that it may not be required the hypothesis of orthogonality anymore for some authors. Without this constraint, The matrix \mathbf{W} may not correspond to the solution of PCA R for an orthogonal projection resulting into principal latent variables $\mathbf{y}_i = R^T \mathbf{x}_i$, like in an usual autoencoder [28] without nonlinearities and deep learning.

Note that the three forms of PCA listed above may be not yet directly converted into a co-clustering setting while the second one is intensively studied for tensors.

Decomposition for m-modes tensor (m=3)

For PCA of a tensor data, there exists also several definitions - called multilinear PCA - which may be not always related to the former ones above and which may be out of the scope herein. When PCA is identified to a factorization, as often in generative models, the nearest and direct implementation of this idea is the **Canonical Polyadic decomposition (CP-D)** and **Tucker decomposition (TK-D)**, see [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37], which finds reduced latent matrices $\xi^{\mathbf{x}(1)}$, $\xi^{\mathbf{x}(2)}$, $\xi^{\mathbf{x}(3)}$ for each mode of the tensor associated to scaling constants aggregated in Λ . Here for three modes:

$$(\hat{\Lambda}, \hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}(1)}, \hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}(2)}, \hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}(3)}) = \begin{cases} \underset{\Lambda, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(1)}, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(2)}, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(3)}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{ijk} \left(x_{ijk} - \sum_s \lambda_s^{\mathbf{x}} \xi_{is}^{\mathbf{x}(1)} \xi_{js}^{\mathbf{x}(2)} \xi_{ks}^{\mathbf{x}(3)} \right)^2, & \text{CP-D} \\ \underset{\Lambda, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(1)}, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(2)}, \xi^{\mathbf{x}(3)}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{ijk} \left(x_{ijk} - \sum_{s_1 s_2 s_3} \lambda_{s_1 s_2 s_3}^{\mathbf{x}} \xi_{i s_1}^{\mathbf{x}(1)} \xi_{j s_2}^{\mathbf{x}(2)} \xi_{k s_3}^{\mathbf{x}(3)} \right)^2, & \text{TK-D.} \end{cases}$$

Note that in order to induce a better fitting, some data may need additional scalars depending on the rows and columns, γ_i and γ_j , to add just after the overall products within the squares above. The algorithm k-means has been already extended to co-clustering before too, hence extending k-means [38] to more modes - thus $m > 2$ - for tensors is natural. By adding the classification variables $\mathbf{z}_\ell = (z_{i_\ell k_\ell})$ for each dimension, and when aggregating the means as $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_{k_1 k_2 k_3})$, it may be written:

$$(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \hat{\mathbf{z}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{z}}_2, \hat{\mathbf{z}}_3) = \underset{\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3}{\operatorname{argmin}} C_{tri}^{123}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3).$$

When this criterion - see Figure 1 for the full expression - is solved, this leads to a tri-clustering of the tensor for three modes -also called more generally co-clustering or clustering or eventually multi-clustering - in the spirit of k-means. An extension comes from adding to the criterion, entropies and replacing the euclidean distance by the log of a density function, which allows to define a new criterion with a probabilistic setting. This extends the former classical mixture model with only one classification variable for the rows or the columns separately, with several classification variables for all the modes simultaneously.

Herein, this is the latent block model which is extended for tensors clustering while including latent variables for the decomposition. The two decompositions presented above are modeled in a more economical way next sections after introducing the multiway latent block model as the backbone of the proposed reduction models and the algorithms for their parameters inference for tensors. Several variants are also considered in order to improve the decomposition and the visualization because this sparse setting can be replaced in order to add more constraints for different results to be compared. While tensors are in large dimensions, tri(-)clustering - as reviewed in [38, 39] - is able to reveal hidden informations from these data such as from matrices before. Note that some classical methods may be mentioned here, with multiway spectral clustering, multiway non negative tensor decomposition (NTF), and non negative (NN) CP/TK-decompositions for tensor with positive values. See also more recent works for tensors via alternative methods based on the distribution of the binary or count values: [40, 41, 42, 43, 19, 44], and closely related to the methods proposed herein. In comparison to existing methods without clustering, a co-clustering or m -clustering is expected to induce faster and eventually better results and better visualizations when its classification matrices are used for the construction of the reduced latent variables. Avoiding the products between matrices or sub-tensors of large full dimensions while also finding summarizing (and eventually overlapping) clusters are both promising for data analysis and machine learning.

Quadratic criteria for m-clustering ($m \geq 3$)

While a co-clustering of the tensor is proposed with LBM herein, the k-means algorithm remains a baseline or a fast alternative for eventually initializations for the reduced latent variables. The more direct way is to end with only one mode and use all the unfolded full slice related to each dimension of the involved mode, such as very high dimensional vectors are to be clustered and eventually reduced via PCA, see KM(ext)

and KM(PCA) [38]. In this paragraph, alternative approaches - see also KM(sum) and InfoCo in [38] - are presented shortly for tensor clustering, for one mode, two-modes and three-modes, see Figure 1 for the related functions to optimize. Here the intermediate values are: $v_{i_1} = \bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet \bullet}^{(2)} - \bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet \bullet}^2$, $z_{i_\ell \bullet} = \sum_{k_\ell} z_{i_\ell k_\ell}$, $v_{i_1 i_2} = \bar{x}_{i_1 i_2 \bullet}^{(2)} - \bar{x}_{i_1 i_2 \bullet}^2$, $v_{i_1 i_3} = \bar{x}_{i_1 i_3 \bullet}^{(2)} - \bar{x}_{i_1 i_3 \bullet}^2$, $v_{i_2 i_3} = \bar{x}_{i_2 i_3 \bullet}^{(2)} - \bar{x}_{i_2 i_3 \bullet}^2$, $\bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet \bullet}^{(2)} = \sum_{i_2 i_3} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3}^2 / n_2 n_3$ and $\bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet \bullet} = \sum_{i_2 i_3} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} / n_2 n_3$, $\bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet i_3}^{(2)} = \sum_{i_2} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3}^2 / n_2$ and $\bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet i_3} = \sum_{i_2} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} / n_2$, $\bar{x}_{i_1 i_2 \bullet}^{(2)} = \sum_{i_3} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3}^2 / n_3$ and $\bar{x}_{i_1 i_2 \bullet} = \sum_{i_3} x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} / n_3$. In practice, the terms v_{i_1} and $v_{i_1 i_2}$ may be neglected as from direct computations of the means for better results. Let review the previous criterion with three sums in the light of tensor clustering, as a first approach to do the work, the related criteria are given in Figure 1.

(a) In a classical k-means for tensor, the clustering is for only one mode of the tensor, say the first one here, but this k-means only performs on reduced values from the tensor, with averages or a reduction [38] instead of full vectors after infolding.

(b) A way to perform a clustering of the tensor is to cluster two dimensions separately only, but for all the modes to be clustered simultaneous as required for a full partitioning. Hence one may write with the sum of

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{km}^1(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1) &= \sum_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_1 k_1} \sum_{i_2 i_3} (x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} - \mu_{k_1})^2 \\
&= n_2 n_3 \left\{ \sum_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_1 k_1} (\bar{x}_{i_1 \bullet \bullet} - \mu_{k_1})^2 + \sum_{i_1} z_{i_1 \bullet} v_{i_1} \right\} \\
C_{co}^{12}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{12}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) &= \sum_{i_1 i_2 k_1 k_2} z_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_2 k_2} \sum_{i_3} (x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} - \mu_{k_1 k_2})^2 \\
&= n_3 \left\{ \sum_{i_1 i_2 k_1 k_2} z_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_2 k_2} (\bar{x}_{i_1 i_2 \bullet} - \mu_{k_1 k_2})^2 + \sum_{i_1 i_2} z_{i_1 \bullet} z_{i_2 \bullet} v_{i_1 i_2} \right\} \\
C_{co}^{13}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{13}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_3) &= n_2 \left\{ \sum_{i_1 i_3 k_1 k_3} z_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_3 k_3} (\bar{x}_{i_1 i_3 \bullet} - \mu_{k_1 k_3})^2 + \sum_{i_1 i_3} z_{i_1 \bullet} z_{i_3 \bullet} v_{i_1 i_3} \right\} \\
C_{co}^{23}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{23}, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3) &= n_1 \left\{ \sum_{i_2 i_3 k_2 k_3} z_{i_2 k_2} z_{i_3 k_3} (\bar{x}_{i_2 i_3 \bullet} - \mu_{k_2 k_3})^2 + \sum_{i_2 i_3} z_{i_2 \bullet} z_{i_3 \bullet} v_{i_2 i_3} \right\} \\
C_{co}^{123}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3) &= \frac{C_{co}^{12}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2)}{n_{12}} + \frac{C_{co}^{13}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_3)}{n_{13}} + \frac{C_{co}^{23}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3)}{n_{23}} \\
C_{tri}^{123}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3) &= \sum_{i_1 i_2 i_3 k_1 k_2 k_3} z_{i_1 k_1} z_{i_2 k_2} z_{i_3 k_3} (x_{i_1 i_2 i_3} - \mu_{k_1 k_2 k_3})^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: Different quadratic criteria related to k-means for a tensor.

three functions for the classification matrices $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3)$, and the means $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_{k_1 k_2}, \mu_{k_1 k_3}, \mu_{k_2 k_3})$, in order to get one unique function to optimize with a classifying likelihood or a matricial version, see [45] for instance. But this does not avoid to prefer to keep the full slice eventually reduced instead of averaged for the three co-clustering. More generally, such averaging leads to:

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{co}^{\ell_1 \ell_2}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\ell_1 \ell_2}, \mathbf{z}_{\ell_1}, \mathbf{z}_{\ell_2}; \mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{i_{\ell_1} i_{\ell_2} k_{\ell_1} k_{\ell_2}} z_{i_{\ell_1} k_{\ell_1}} z_{i_{\ell_2} k_{\ell_2}} F_{\ell}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\ell_1 \ell_2}; \mathbf{x}) \\
C_{co}^{1 \dots m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_m; \mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{\ell_1 \ell_2 < \ell_1} \sum_{\ell_2 < \ell_1} \frac{C_{co}^{\ell_1 \ell_2}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\ell_1 \ell_2}, \mathbf{z}_{\ell_1}, \mathbf{z}_{\ell_2}; \mathbf{x})}{n_{\ell_1 \ell_2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Here $n_{\ell_1 \ell_2}$ is some constant, while $F_{\ell}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\ell_1 \ell_2})$ is the function with parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\ell_1 \ell_2}$ - aggregated in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ - for the co-clustering such as the quadratic above or a distribution. Hence, each co-clustering $C_{co}^{\ell_1 \ell_2}$ deals with only two modes for the clustering, hence adding simultaneously the functions leads to a full clustering of the tensor. This is not the criterion in stake herein but instead the third one with a triple sum.

(c) When solving for the alternative unique criterion given before with C_{tri}^{123} , one gets to solve also for three criteria at the first step for the classifications matrices $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{z}_3)$, one for each mode, before solving for the the means $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_{k_1 k_2 k_3})$ in an iterative procedure or loop. This criterion is related to the proposed model next section when $m = 3$ instead of $m > 2$ and with a Gaussian distribution when variances and priors are equal in all the blocks, see the first publications in co-clustering.

Generalized criterion from LBM for m-clustering (m=3)

If a quadratic distance is to be optimize, here, in the general case, any function may be involved. Indeed, let denote $f(\cdot)$, a function of the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ in a block - aggregated in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ - with observation $x_{i_1 i_2 i_3}$, such that for instance:

A function to solve for a tensor co-clustering may be written instead of C_{tri}^{123} as follows, with now $z_{i_\ell k_\ell}$

Name	Function	$f(x_{i_1^3}, \theta_{k_1^3})$
Quadratic		$-(x_{i_1^3} - \alpha_{k_1^3})^2$
Quantile 0.5		$- (x_{i_1^3} - \alpha_{k_1^3}) $
Gaussian	$\log \varphi_N(x_{i_1^3}; \theta_{k_1^3})$	$-\frac{(x_{i_1^3} - \alpha_{k_1^3})^2}{2\sigma_{k_1^3}^2} - \frac{\log(2\pi\sigma_{k_1^3}^2)}{2}$
Bernoulli	$\log \varphi_B(x_{i_1^3}; \theta_{k_1^3})$	$\log(\alpha_{k_1^3})^{x_{i_1^3}} + \log(1 - \alpha_{k_1^3})^{1-x_{i_1^3}}$
Poisson	$\log \varphi_P(x_{i_1^3}; \theta_{k_1^3})$	$-\lambda_{k_1^3}^{x_{i_1^3}} + x_{i_1^3} \log(\lambda_{k_1^3}) - \log x_{i_1^3}!$
Multinoulli	$\log \varphi_M(x_{i_1^3}; \theta_{k_1^3})$	$\sum_{h=1}^H x_{i_1^3}^{(h)} \log \alpha_{k_1^3, h}, \sum_{h=1}^H \alpha_{k_1^3, h} = 1$

Table 1: Examples of functions for generalized criterion of LBM.

not anymore binary but fuzzy replaced by $c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell$ in $]0; 1[$ and aggregated in \mathbf{c}^ℓ , with,

$$C_{tri,f}^{123}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{c}^1, \mathbf{c}^2, \mathbf{c}^3) = \sum_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \sum_{k_1 k_2 k_3} c_{i_1 k_1}^1 c_{i_2 k_2}^2 c_{i_3 k_3}^3 f(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k_1 k_2 k_3}) - \sum_{\ell} \sum_{i_\ell, k_\ell} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell \log c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell + \sum_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \sum_{k_1 k_2 k_3} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell P_{\ell k_\ell}.$$

The idea of tri-clustering next after will be to optimize in an alternated way for $c_{i_1 k_1}^1, c_{i_2 k_2}^2, c_{i_3 k_3}^3$ at a first step and all the parameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ at the second step. The latent block model comes to this solution thanks to a probabilistic setting via a statistical parametric likelihood approximated by the function above for the inference of the parameters. But if under this model, the function $f(\cdot)$ is generally a density probability function or a mass probability function, it is clear that other function may be used here, like robust distances for instance. Next, mostly the Bernoulli, Gaussian and Poisson probability functions for $f(\cdot)$ are discussed in order to deal with tensors with binary, continuous or count values.

3 Multiway latent block model (WLBM)

A review of the latent block model and its general definition summarizes briefly the modeling foundation before presenting our proposal in this section.

3.1 Former 2-modes model and algorithm ($m = 2$)

Model LBM (or W_2 LBM)

Within the context of the classical mixture model for a matrix with n rows and d columns, a partition of I into g clusters is represented by the binary classification matrix $\mathbf{z} = (z_{ik})_{n \times g}$ such that $\sum_{k=1}^g z_{ik} = 1$ and $z_{ik} = 1$ indicates the component of the row i . Just as I is partitioned into g clusters, columns can be partitioned into m clusters by the binary classification matrix $\mathbf{w} = (w_{j\ell})_{d \times m}$. If the most usual clustering methods deal with partitioning of only a set of rows $(x_i)_{i=1}^{i=n}$ with indices $I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ or eventually a set of columns $(x_j)_{j=1}^{j=d}$ with indices $J = \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$, co-clustering is interested in the clustering of both simultaneously. The set of all possible assignments \mathbf{w} of J (resp. \mathbf{z} of I) is denoted \mathcal{W} (resp. \mathcal{Z}). The $n \times d$ random variables generating the observed x_{ij} cells of the data matrix are assumed to be independent in LBM, once \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{w} are fixed. For the parameters optimization, the completed data are taken to be the vector $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w})$ where the latent variables \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w} are the random labels for the rows and the columns respectively. Let denote the different density and mass functions as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}) = \prod_{i,k} (p_k)^{z_{ik}} \prod_{j,\ell} (q_\ell)^{z_{j\ell}} = P(\mathbf{z})P(\mathbf{w})$$

$$P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}) = \prod_{i,i,k,\ell} \varphi(x_{ij}; \theta_{k\ell})^{z_{ik} w_{j\ell}}.$$

Model	pdf of cell (k_1^m)	φ	$A(\alpha_{k_1^m}^m)$	$B(\alpha_{k_1^m}^m)$	$\beta_{i_1^m}$	$\alpha_{k_1^m}$	$x_{i_1^m}$
G- W_m LBM	$\mathcal{N}(\alpha_{k_1^m}; \sigma_{k_1^m})$	$\frac{\exp(-(x_{i_1^m} - \alpha_{k_1^m})^2 / 2\sigma_{k_1^m}^2)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{k_1^m}}$	$\alpha_{k_1^m} / \sigma_{k_1^m}^2$	$\alpha_{k_1^m}^2 / 2\sigma_{k_1^m}^2$	1	\mathbb{R}	\mathbb{R}
B- W_m LBM	$\mathcal{B}(\alpha_{k_1^m})$	$(\alpha_{k_1^m})^{x_{i_1^m}} (1 - \alpha_{k_1^m})^{1 - x_{i_1^m}}$	$\log \frac{\alpha_{k_1^m}}{1 - \alpha_{k_1^m}}$	$-\log(1 - \alpha_{k_1^m})$	1	$[0; 1]$	$\{0, 1\}$
P- W_m LBM	$\mathcal{P}(\beta_{i_1^m} \alpha_{k_1^m})$	$\frac{\exp(-\beta_{i_1^m} \alpha_{k_1^m}) (\beta_{i_1^m} \alpha_{k_1^m})^{x_{i_1^m}}}{x_{i_1^m}!}$	$\log \beta_{i_1^m} \alpha_{k_1^m}$	$\beta_{i_1^m} \alpha_{k_1^m}$	$\prod_{\ell} \mu_{i_{\ell}}$	$[0; 1]$	\mathbb{N}_+
P ₁ - W_m LBM	$\mathcal{P}(\alpha_{k_1^m})$	$\frac{\exp(-\alpha_{k_1^m}) (\alpha_{k_1^m})^{x_{i_1^m}}}{x_{i_1^m}!}$	$\log \alpha_{k_1^m}$	$\alpha_{k_1^m}$	1	\mathbb{R}_+	\mathbb{N}_+
M- W_m LBM	$\mathcal{M}(\alpha_{k_1^m})$	$\prod_{h=1}^H \alpha_{k_1^m, h}^{x_{i_1^m, h}^{(h)}}$	$\left[\log \frac{\alpha_{k_1^m, 1}}{\alpha_{k_1^m, H}}, \dots, \log \frac{\alpha_{k_1^m, H-1}}{\alpha_{k_1^m, H}}, 0 \right]^T$	$-\log(1 - \sum_{h=1}^{H-1} \alpha_{k_1^m, h})$	1	$[0; 1]$	$[0; 1]^{\otimes H}$

Table 2: Examples of p.d.f. or p.m.f. with ($\beta_{i_1^m} = \mu_{i_1} \cdots \mu_{i_m}$ and $\mu_{i_{\ell}} = \sum_{i_m} x_{i_1 \dots i_m}$), from $\varphi_E(x_{i_1^m}; \theta) = e^{(x_{i_1^m} A(\alpha_{k_1^m}^m) - B(\alpha_{k_1^m}^m) + C(x_{i_1^m}))}$.

The classification or completed log-likelihood L_C can then be written conditionnally to all the labels at each mode:

$$L_C(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}; \mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \log P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}) + \log P(\mathbf{z}) + \log P(\mathbf{w}).$$

Hence, with the data \mathbf{x} seen as a set of cells $(x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{ij}, \dots, x_{nd})$, these observations are independently generated conditionnally to the row and columns labels. The two sets of possible assignments \mathbf{w} and \mathbf{z} aggregate the cells of the matrix \mathbf{x} into a number of contiguous, non-overlapping blocks. The following sum is obtained [12] by independence of \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{w} , by summing over all the assignments $\mathcal{Z} \times \mathcal{W}$ of rows and columns clusters:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{LBM}(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}) &= \sum_{(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w})} e^{L_C(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}; \mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta})} \\ &= \sum_{(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w})} \prod_{i,k} p_k^{z_{ik}} \prod_{j,\ell} q_{\ell}^{w_{j\ell}} \prod_{i,j,k,\ell} \varphi(x_{ij}; \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k\ell})^{z_{ik} w_{j\ell}}. \end{aligned}$$

Here $\varphi(\cdot; \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k\ell})$ is a probability function defined on the real line \mathbb{R} or the set of integers \mathbb{N} , while $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k\ell}; 1 \leq k \leq g, 1 \leq \ell \leq m\}$ are the unknown parameters. The vectors of the probabilities p_k and q_{ℓ} that a row and a column belong to the k^{th} component and to the ℓ^{th} component are respectively denoted $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_g)$ and $\mathbf{q} = (q_1, \dots, q_m)$. The set of parameters is denoted $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and is compound of \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} plus $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ which aggregates the $g \times m$ scalar $\alpha_{k\ell}$ via the matrix $(\alpha_{k\ell})$. Hereafter, to simplify the notation, the sums and the products relating to rows, columns or clusters will be subscripted respectively by the letters i, j, k , or ℓ for matrices and more generally i_1, i_1, \dots, i_m and k_1, k_1, \dots, k_m for tensors, without indicating the limits of variation, which are implicit.

The set of parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of the model can be estimated by maximizing the log-likelihood:

$$L(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \mathbf{x}) = \log f_{LBM}(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}).$$

A particular distribution is needed for the cells, for continuous, binary and contingency matrices with originally Gaussian, Bernoulli and Poisson distributions where the parameters are expectations plus sometimes other parameters, say $(\mu_{k\ell}$ or $\alpha_{k\ell}, \sigma_{k\ell})$, $\alpha_{k\ell}$ and $\lambda_{k\ell}^{ij} = \mu_i \nu_j \alpha_{k\ell}$ respectively. Note that the effects $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_n)$ and $\boldsymbol{\nu} = (\nu_1, \dots, \nu_d)$ are assumed equal to the following constant margin totals by rows and by columns, $\mu_i = \sum_j x_{ij}$ for $i \in I$ and $\nu_j = \sum_i x_{ij}$ for $j \in J$ for contingency matrices.

Objective function and optimization algorithm

For the proposed model with the introduced constraints, we aim to address the problem of the estimation of the parameters by a maximum likelihood (ML) approach such that:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} L(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \mathbf{x}).$$

Let us focus on the estimation of a value of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ by the maximum likelihood approach associated to the block mixture model. For this model, the complete data are $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w})$ where the unobservable vectors \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{w} are the

Model	$\log \frac{c_{i\ell k\ell}^{(t)}}{P_{i\ell k\ell}^{(t)}} \propto \sum_{I_m^\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \log \varphi(x_{i_1^m}; \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t)})$	
G-W _m LBM	$\propto \sum_{I_m^\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \log \varphi_N(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m})$	$\propto - \sum_{\mathcal{X}_m^\ell} \left[\frac{x_{k_1^m; 2}^{(t)} - 2x_{k_1^m; 1}^{(t)} \alpha_{k_1^m} + c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} (\alpha_{k_1^m}^2 + 2\sigma_{k_1^m}^2 \log \sigma_{k_1^m})}{2\sigma_{k_1^m}^2} \right]$
B-W _m LBM	$\propto \sum_{I_m^\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \log \varphi_B(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m})$	$\propto \sum_{\mathcal{X}_m^\ell} \left[x_{k_1^m; 1}^{(t)} \log(\theta_{k_1^m}) + (c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} - x_{k_1^m; 1}^{(t)}) \log(1 - \theta_{k_1^m}) \right]$
P-W _m LBM	$\propto \sum_{I_m^\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \log \varphi_P(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m})$	$\propto \sum_{\mathcal{X}_m^\ell} \left[- \sum_{I_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \lambda_{k_1^m}^{i_1^m} + \sum_{I_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} x_{i_1^m} \log(\lambda_{k_1^m}^{i_1^m}) - x_{i_1^m; L}^{(t)} \right]$
M-W _m LBM	$\propto \sum_{I_m^\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^\ell} c_{i\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} \log \varphi_M(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m})$	$\propto \sum_{\mathcal{X}_m^\ell} \left[\sum_{h=1}^H x_{k_1^m; 1, h}^{(t)} \log \alpha_{k_1^m, h} \right]$

Table 3: Posterior probabilities for the E-step from BEM with the multiway model WLBm.

labels. The complete log-likelihood of $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w})$ leads to an Expectation-maximization algorithm (EM) [46] in two steps, where the E-step is intractable, thus an alternative approach has been proposed in the literature.

An approach based on a Generalized EM and a variational approximation by the product $c_{ik}^{(t)} d_{j\ell}^{(t)}$ has been proposed previously in the literature, and named *Block EM* (BEM). Here it is denoted the variational probabilities c_{ik} such that $\sum_k c_{ik} = 1$, and also $d_{j\ell}$ such that $\sum_\ell d_{j\ell} = 1$. Their matricial representations are respectively $\mathbf{c} = (c_{ik})$, and $\mathbf{d} = (d_{j\ell})$, such that the variational distribution for the clustering is defined as $Q_{(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d})}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}) = \prod_{i,k} (c_{ik})^{z_{ik}} \prod_{j,\ell} (d_{j\ell})^{w_{j\ell}}$. Then, by the Jensen inequality a bound $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$ can be defined for the intractable loglikelihood function. After defining this lower bound of the log-likelihood (see [15]), the algorithm maximizes, instead of $L(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \mathbf{x})$, this alternative surrogate function:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}; \boldsymbol{\theta}) &= \sum_{i,j,k,\ell} c_{ik} d_{j\ell} \log \varphi(x_{ij}; \theta_{k\ell}) \\ &+ \sum_{i,k} c_{ik} (p_k - \log c_{ik}) + \sum_{j,\ell} d_{j\ell} (q_\ell - \log d_{j\ell}). \end{aligned}$$

Then, it repeats until convergence the two following steps:

- **E-step** The posterior probabilities $\mathbf{e} = (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d})$ are found at the current time step (t) by maximizing \mathcal{F} with respect to c_{ik} and $d_{j\ell}$ with the normalizing constraint of summing to one while $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}$, hence leading:

$$(\mathbf{c}^{(t)}, \mathbf{d}^{(t)}) = \operatorname{argmax}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}).$$

- **M-step** A temporary value of the parameters is found for the next current time step $(t+1)$ by maximizing \mathcal{F} with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ while $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}^{(t)}$ from previous step. Say:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^{(t+1)} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \tilde{Q}_{LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}).$$

Where, $\tilde{Q}_{LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{c}^{(t)}, \mathbf{d}^{(t)}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$. The optimization provides the updated solutions $\alpha_{k\ell}^{(t+1)}$, $p_k^{(t+1)}$, $q_\ell^{(t+1)}$ and eventually other parameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, after derivatives equated to zero.

Hence, the parameters are estimated by an iterative way, the BEM algorithm proceeds by an alternated maximization of \tilde{Q} and converges to a final solution which maximizes (locally) the log-likelihood of the latent block model. A hat is added to each parameter or statistics which is estimated and found at the final stage of the inference algorithm.

3.2 Multiway version and parameterization ($m \geq 2$)

Co-clustering methods are dedicated to the detection of the main homogeneous sub-structures in a data cloud when the variables can be clustered. At the end, one has a small matrix $\alpha_{k\ell}$ which can be considered as a very synthetic view of the dataset. The new multiway version is defined in this section for changing a 2-dimensional problem into a m -dimensional problem. The (co-)clustering tackles the modes/sides of a tensor

$\mathbf{x} = x_{i_1, \dots, i_m} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times \dots \times n_m}$ with m the number of modes of the tensor, from now until the end. Thus, one may denote that:

$$\begin{aligned} I_m &= \{i_1, \dots, i_m\} \in \{1, \dots, n_1\} \times \dots \times \{1, \dots, n_m\} \\ \mathcal{K}_m &= \{k_1, \dots, k_m\} \in \{1, \dots, g_1\} \times \dots \times \{1, \dots, g_m\}, \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is denoted here $i_\ell \in \{1, \dots, n_\ell\}$ for the mode ℓ of the tensor, and $k_\ell \in \{1, \dots, g_\ell\}$ for the number of clusters g_ℓ of the mode ℓ of the tensor. One gets for the new random variables/matrices for the clustering along of each mode, $\mathbf{z}_\ell = (z_{i_\ell k_\ell})$ for $\ell \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. To summarize, from the 2-modes to the m -modes, it is replaced i by i_1 , j by i_2 , and added the new indices i_3, \dots, i_m for the additional modes. Such that also z becomes z_1 , w becomes z_2 to which are added z_3, \dots, z_m and so on for the other quantities, with $(p_k)_k$ replaced by $(p_{1k_1})_{k_1}$, q_ℓ replaced by $(p_{2k_2})_{k_2}$ to which are also added the new priors $(p_{3k_3})_{k_3}, \dots, (p_{mk_m})_{k_m}$. Here, the probabilities $p_{\ell k_\ell}$ that a mode of the tensor belongs to the k_ℓ^{th} component are aggregated into,

$$\mathbf{p}_\ell = (p_{\ell k_\ell})_{1 \leq k_\ell \leq g_\ell} = (p_{\ell 1}, \dots, p_{\ell g_\ell}) \text{ for } \ell = 1, \dots, m.$$

Also the posterior probabilities are $c_{i_1 k_1}^1$ and $c_{i_2 k_2}^2$ replacing the previous c_{ik} and $d_{j\ell}$ such that it is added for the new modes $c_{i_3 k_3}^3, \dots, c_{i_m k_m}^m$, with the matrices,

$$\mathbf{C}^\ell = (c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell)_{i_\ell \in \{1, \dots, n_\ell\}, k_\ell \in \{1, \dots, g_\ell\}} \text{ for } \ell = 1, \dots, m.$$

Similarly, the criteria are rewritten by summing to the new variables and new modes, in order to get the extension to a tensor of any dimensions. The corresponding expressions are presented in the following just after before the optimization which introduces new latent vectors to be estimated.

Model W_m LBM for m -modes tensor

The new required expressions are for the likelihood $f_{W_m \text{LBM}}$, the update formula of the corresponding variational probabilities $c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^\ell$, and the maximization for the M-step optimizing w.r.t the parameters $\theta_{\mathcal{X}_m}$, is defined by following the previous 2-dimensional matrix extended into a m -dimensional tensor, with $x_{i_1^m} = x_{i_1 \dots i_m}$, $\theta_{k_1^m} = \theta_{k_1 \dots k_m}$, and also Z_m for the indices from $(\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_m)$,

$$f_{W_m \text{LBM}}(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{Z_m} \prod_{\ell=1}^m \prod_{i_\ell k_\ell} p_{\ell k_\ell}^{z_{i_\ell k_\ell}} \prod_{I_m, \mathcal{X}_m} \varphi(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m})^{z_{i_1 k_1} \dots z_{i_m k_m}}.$$

This leads also to the variational bound which is maximized w.r.t. m clustering variables instead of just 2 ones before, when adding the indice ℓ for the posterior and prior of each mode ℓ in order to a better readability, while $\ell = 1, \dots, m$ and $i_\ell = 1, \dots, n_\ell$:

$$c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} \propto p_{\ell k_\ell}^{(t)} \exp \left(\sum_{I_m \setminus i_\ell, \mathcal{X}_m \setminus k_\ell} \left[\prod_{o \neq \ell} c_{i_o k_o}^{o(t)} \right] \log \varphi(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m}^{(t)}) \right).$$

Similarly, just the maximum may be preferred for a classifying version of BEM, called BCEM, for binary variables instead of fuzzy ones. For maximizing the new function \mathcal{F} with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the objective function becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Q}_{W_m \text{LBM}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) &= \sum_{I_m, \mathcal{X}_m} c_{i_1 k_1}^{1(t)} \dots c_{i_m k_m}^{m(t)} \log \varphi(x_{i_1^m}; \theta_{k_1^m}^{(t)}) \\ &+ \sum_{\ell=1}^m \sum_{i_\ell, k_\ell} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} p_{\ell k_\ell} - \sum_{\ell=1}^m \sum_{i_\ell, k_\ell} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} \log c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

There was just changed the indices, as the algebra remains the same: this defines our multiway latent block model and its corresponding parameters inference. The new M-step solves for the optimization:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t+1)} = \tilde{Q}_{W_m \text{LBM}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}).$$

The expressions for the variational expectation step with the posterior probabilities of any cluster of indice k_ℓ for mode ℓ in a m -modes tensor for three case of data are given in Table 2. Here it is denoted $i_1^m =$

Model	Criterion
Unconstrained	$\tilde{Q}_{GW_3LBM}((\alpha_{k_3})_{\mathcal{X}_3}, (\sigma_{k_3})_{\mathcal{X}_3}, \mathbf{p}) \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) = \tilde{Q}_{W_mLBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)})$
Sparse	$\tilde{Q}_{SGW_3LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta} \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) = \tilde{Q}_{GW_3LBM}((\boldsymbol{\tau}^T \xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}), (\sigma_{k_1 k_2 k_3}), \mathbf{p}) \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)})$
Constrained	$\tilde{Q}_{SGW_3LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta} \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) = \tilde{Q}_{GW_3LBM}((\boldsymbol{\tau}^T \tilde{\xi}_{k_1 k_2 k_3}), (\sigma_{k_1 k_2 k_3}), \mathbf{p}) \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) + \lambda F(\tilde{\xi}_{k_1 k_2 k_3})$
Decomposition	$\tilde{Q}_{PCAW_3LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta} \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) = \tilde{Q}_{GW_3LBM}((\Lambda \oplus_s \xi_{k_1} \oplus_s \xi_{k_2} \oplus_s \xi_{k_3}), (\sigma_{k_1 k_2 k_3}), \mathbf{p}) \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)})$

Table 4: Models from the likelihood of WLBm with $m = 3$ and $\varphi = \varphi_N$, with parameters $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = (\sigma_{k_3}^2) \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^{g_1 \times g_2 \times g_3}$ and $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_{k_3}) \in \mathbb{R}^{g_1 \times g_2 \times g_3}$.

$i_1 \cdots i_m, k_1^m = k_1 \cdots k_m$ as indices and $I_m^{\setminus \ell} = I_m \setminus i_\ell, \mathcal{X}_m^{\setminus \ell} = \mathcal{X}_m \setminus k_\ell$ as sets. While $x_{k_1^m;1}^{\setminus \ell(t)} = \sum_{I_m^{\setminus \ell}} c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{\setminus \ell(t)} x_{i_1}^m, x_{k_1^m;2}^{\setminus \ell(t)} = \sum_{I_m^{\setminus \ell}} c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{\setminus \ell(t)} x_{i_1}^m, x_{k_1^m;L}^{\setminus \ell(t)} = \sum_{I_m^{\setminus \ell}} c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{\setminus \ell(t)} \log x_{i_1}^m!$, $c_{k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} = \sum_{i_\ell} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)}$, and $c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{\setminus \ell(t)} = \prod_{o \neq \ell} c_{i_\ell k_o}^{o(t)}$, while $c_{k_1^m}^{\setminus \ell(t)} = \prod_{o \neq \ell} c_{k_o}^{o(t)}$. For the solution for the maximization step, let denote, $x_{k_1^m;1}^{(t)} = \sum_{I_m} c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} x_{i_1}^m, x_{k_1^m;2}^{(t)} = \sum_{I_m} c_{i_\ell k_1^m}^{(t)} x_{i_1}^m, c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} = \prod_{\ell} c_{k_\ell}^{\ell(t)}$, and $c_{k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} = \sum_{i_\ell} c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t)}$, for the mode ℓ of the tensor and $k_\ell \in \{1, \dots, g_\ell\}$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)} &= x_{i_1^m;1}^{(t)} / c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} \quad \text{and} \quad p_{\ell k_\ell}^{(t+1)} = c_{k_\ell}^{\ell(t)} / n_\ell \\ \sigma_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)} &= \sqrt{\left(x_{k_1^m;2}^{(t)} - 2x_{k_1^m;1}^{(t)} \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)} + c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)2} \right) / c_{k_1^m}^{(t)}} \\ \sigma^{(t+1)} &= \sqrt{\sum_{\mathcal{X}_m} \left(x_{k_1^m;2}^{(t)} - 2x_{k_1^m;1}^{(t)} \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)} + c_{k_1^m}^{(t)} \alpha_{k_1^m}^{(t+1)2} \right) / \sum_{\mathcal{X}_m} c_{k_1^m}^{(t)}}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, the updates are for φ_B and φ_G mostly. Note that some constraints may be better for $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ too, as for instance all variances equal to $\sigma_{k_1^m} = \sigma$ or eventually only for clusters from one given mode, leading to a similar but different expression. When constraints are added, multidimensional latent vectors are estimated instead of directly the centers $\mu_{k_1^m}$ or $\alpha_{k_1^m}$ from the blocks.

Related and extended models

As a generalized model, the multiway latent block model counts as particular cases several former models from the literature. With diverse distribution functions for the cells in the blocks - see the Table 2 revisited from [18] for tensors - it results different expressions for the posterior probabilities in Table 3, estimation step and maximization step with particular regularizations on the parameters such as diverse model were introduced early in the literature when the LBM was created for co-clustering of matrices.

- The more related researches are a multi-view LBM [47], a multivariate LBM [42], and a 3-modes Poisson LBM [41] illustrating the relevance of BEM for tensors.
- Constrained model with a reparameterization [18] of the parameters with reductions of the dimensions. See the Gaussian case for instance in Table 4 as explained at the next section.
- Constrained model with a sparsification of the parameters, with constraints on parameters. The diagonal version [48, 49] is written in the proposed model with parameterizing vectors: one latent $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and ones observed for the cells in the tensor $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ for more generality. The purpose is to induce constraints in a generic way on the contrary to the "sparse" diagonal case for instance which supposes that the vocabulary is separated for each cluster in the case of textual classes, while an additional perspective may be to find automatically non binary constraints or at least binary ones via a relaxation for instance. See in the Gaussian case for instance in Table 4, leading to an equivalence between the diagonal approach and the proposed parameterization with well chosen¹ binary vectors $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$. Note that an alternative, for this equality of the means in the blocks with a regression, is to keep a full model with $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ equal

¹For $m = 3$ and $g_1 = g_2 = g_3 = g$, let define the vectors $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ with ξ_{kkk} equal to the basis vector of \mathcal{R}^g completed by a $g + 1$ component equal to zero, and with $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ equal to a vector with $g + 1$ components where only the last one $g + 1$ component equal to one and equal to zero otherwise: $[1, 0, \dots, 0, 0], [0, 1, \dots, 0, 0], \dots, [0, 0, \dots, 1, 0], [0, 0, \dots, 0, 1]$ such that the solution for $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, when denoting $h_{k_1 k_2 k_3} = c_{k_1}^{1(t)} c_{k_2}^{2(t)} c_{k_3}^{3(t)} / \sigma_{k_1 k_2 k_3}^{(t+1)}$ and $h_{k_1 k_2 k_3}^x = \sum_{I_m} c_{i_1 k_1}^{1(t)} c_{i_2 k_2}^{2(t)} c_{i_3 k_3}^{3(t)} / \sigma_{k_1 k_2 k_3}^{(t+1)}$ becomes the same solution than for the diagonal

to one of the basis vectors of $\mathcal{R}^{g_1 \times g_2 \times g_3}$, and to add the constraint externally similarly than an usual restricted regression, such that, one may write when keeping only r clusters, as defined via the matrix R :

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\tau} \tilde{Q}_{SGW_3LBM}(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}) \text{ s.c. } \Psi R = O_r,$$

leads to the new estimate $\tau^{(t+1)}$ with the constraints but this approach supposes the constraints known on the contrary to the previous model which is more flexible. In both cases, it becomes possible just before the regression to optimize for the vector $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ during the iterative loop by relaxing the hypothesis of binary values. For instance with $\tilde{\xi}_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ a vector of softmax functions with common denominators and unknown parameters, while $F(\cdot)$ is an usual function for the norm penalty such as entropy or L_1 -norm, see Table 4.

- A closely related model is also the Tensor Block Model (TBM) in [50]. This model is generalized herein with a probabilistic framework but also allows to justify the model. For TBM, in the case of Gaussian cells and common known variance, the statistical convergence of the resulting estimator and the partition consistency of the algorithm for TBM was shown. Even if this theoretical result is out of the scope herein, it suggests that WLBM is able to reach relevant parameters when well fitted and when enough are data in the clusters.

In summary, if there are some correspondences of the previous models with the multiway variant, each particular model has its own properties or implementations without embedding latent variables. In the following, the focus is on the low dimensional reductions of a tensor with the proposed clustering model.

4 PCA Multiway Latent Block Model

This section discussed a reparameterization with low dimensional matrices of the center in the blocks.

4.1 Decomposition/factorization for m -modes tensor

Following the classical tensor algebra [33], the two main decompositions may be in stake via a cell-wise function $\phi(\cdot)$ such as identity, exponential or sigmoidal ones, with the reduced latent variables when denoting $\lambda_{s_1^m} = \lambda_{s_1, \dots, s_m}$ and S_m for all the indices from (s_1, \dots, s_m) ,

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^\ell &= (\xi_{ks}^\ell)_{ks} \in \mathbb{R}^{g_\ell \times r_\ell} \text{ for } \ell = 1, \dots, m \\ \Lambda &= \begin{cases} (\lambda_s)_{s_1} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times 1} & , \text{ CP-D} \\ (\lambda_{s_1^m})_{s_1^m} \in \mathbb{R}^{r_1 \times \dots \times r_m} & , \text{ TK-D.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, with eventually $r_m = r$, as the tensor to reduce is now $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ instead of \mathbf{x} , one may write the decomposition with $\Lambda, \xi^{(1)}, \dots, \xi^{(m)}$ unknown and:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k_1 \dots k_m} \approx \phi \left(\Lambda \oplus_s \xi_{k_1}^1 \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \xi_{k_m}^m \right).$$

case:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau^{(t+1)} &= \left(\sum_{\mathcal{X}_3} \frac{c_{k_1^3}^{(t)}}{\sigma_{k_1^3}^{(t)2}} \xi_{k_1^3}^T \xi_{k_1^3} \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{\mathcal{X}_3} \frac{x_{k_1^3}^{(t)}}{\sigma_{k_1^3}^{(t)2}} \xi_{k_1^3} \right) \\ &= \left[\begin{array}{cccc} h_{111}^x & h_{222}^x & \dots & \frac{h_{ggg}^x}{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}} \frac{\sum h_{k_1 k_2 k_3}^x}{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}} \\ h_{111} & h_{222} & \dots & h_{ggg} \frac{\sum h_{k_1 k_2 k_3}}{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}} \end{array} \right]^T \\ &= \left[\begin{array}{cccc} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{111}^{(t+1)} & \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{222}^{(t+1)} & \dots & \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ggg}^{(t+1)} \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ooo}^{(t+1)} \end{array} \right]^T. \end{aligned}$$

Then the different binary vectors $\xi_{k_1 k_2 k_3}$ selects one of these components. Hence, with $\mathcal{X}_{\text{dia}} = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}_{k_1=k_2=k_3}$, $\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}} = \{k_1, k_2, k_3\}_{k_1 \neq k_2 \neq k_3}$ and $x_{\bullet\bullet\bullet} = \sum_{I_3} x_{i_1^3}$, as $\sum_{\mathcal{X}_3} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k_1^3}^{(t+1)} c_{k_1^3}^{(t)} = x_{\bullet\bullet\bullet}$, the equality constraint induces that the common value is equal to:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ooo}^{(t+1)} = \left(x_{\bullet\bullet\bullet} - \sum_{I_3, \mathcal{X}_{\text{dia}}} \frac{c_{i_1^3}^{(t)} x_{i_1^3}^{(t)}}{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}} \right) / \sum_{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}} \frac{c_{k_1^3}^{(t)}}{\mathcal{X}_{\text{off}}}.$$

Where:

$$\Lambda \oplus_s \xi_{k_1}^1 \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \xi_{k_m}^m = \begin{cases} \sum_s \lambda_s \xi_{k_1 s}^1 \xi_{k_2 s}^2 \dots \xi_{k_m s}^m, & \text{CP-D} \\ \sum_{S_m} \lambda_{s_1} \xi_{k_1 s_1}^1 \xi_{k_2 s_2}^2 \dots \xi_{k_m s_m}^m, & \text{TK-D.} \end{cases}$$

This expression extends the scalar product between vectors [17] (as previously proposed) to a tensor decomposition with latent matrices $\xi_{k_\ell s_\ell}^\ell$ to be estimated for all ℓ and s_ℓ . The family of new models is related to a CP decomposition and for more generality to a Tucker decomposition from theory in tensor algebra. The difference here is that this is the summarizing tensor from the latent block model which is decomposed as illustrated for $m = 3$ in Figure 2 where the sum is from the posterior probabilities.

Figure 2: (CP/TK) decomposition + WLBm for a 3-modes tensor.

This is useful in many domains such as visualization, reduction, and factorization or even predictive methods because of the reducing matrices along each mode. To study further the parameterization, four variants may be implemented as presented in the Table 5 below. For a grid constraint, $\xi = \Omega \check{\xi}_{k_1}$ with $\check{\xi}_{k_1}$ constant aligned [17, 18] and the matrix Ω becomes the latent variable for inference of the projected mode.

Name	$\alpha_{k_1^3}$	constr. ξ_{k_1}	constr. $\xi_{k_2} \dots \xi_{k_m}$
D-F-m	$\Lambda \oplus_s \xi_{k_1} \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \xi_{k_m}$	no	no
D-F-1	$\Lambda \oplus_s \xi_{k_1} \oplus_s \xi_{k_2}^m$	no	no
D-G-m	$\Lambda \oplus_s \Omega \check{\xi}_{k_1} \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \xi_{k_m}$	grid	no
D-G-1	$\Lambda \oplus_s \Omega \check{\xi}_{k_1} \oplus_s \xi_{k_2}^m$	grid	no

Table 5: Latent variables for tensor parameters α in WLBm.

	Sizes for \mathbf{x}	Sizes for α	Ratio
CP-D	$\sum_\ell n_\ell r$	$\sum_\ell g_\ell r$	$= \frac{g_0}{n_0}$
TK-D	$\sum_\ell n_\ell r_\ell + r_1 r_2 \dots r_\ell$	$\sum_\ell g_\ell r_\ell + r_1 r_2 \dots r_\ell$	$\approx \frac{g_0 + r_0^{m-1}}{n_0 + r_0^{m-1}}$

Table 6: Example of size for the reduced views of the tensors

The four cases are related to an approximated decompositions CP-D or TK-D for D-F-m and D-F-1 while PCA-m and PCA-1 are even more closely for an approximated PCA decomposition. The parameters are not any more completely free, for this version of principal component analysis, as instead this is a regular grid which allows to have an ordering on the plane [17, 16, 18] as wanted for visualization purposes. A last case may be an hybrid model with decomposition on the diagonals (i.e. mean parameterized with the latent vectors) and identical values in the other blocks (i.e. mean parameterized without the latent vectors or at least with some common values), hence with equality per slice or global to non diagonal blocks. Flexibility of the model allows many particular case as constraints for a better fitting of a given tensor data.

4.2 Post-treatments

After the inference of the parameters, diverse approaches are available for data analysis from the obtained final latent variables.

Reconstruction of cells

From the decomposition of the tensor to the dimensions $r_1 \times \dots \times r_m$, the reconstruction of the cells remains as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_{i_1}^m &= \sum_{\mathcal{K}_m} \hat{c}_{i_1 k_1}^1 \hat{c}_{i_2 k_2}^2 \dots \hat{c}_{i_m k_m}^m \beta_{i_1}^m \hat{\alpha}_{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m} \\ &\approx \sum_{\mathcal{K}_m} \hat{c}_{i_1 k_1}^1 \hat{c}_{i_2 k_2}^2 \dots \hat{c}_{i_m k_m}^m \beta_{i_1}^m \phi \left(\hat{\Lambda} \oplus_s \hat{\xi}_{k_1}^1 \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \hat{\xi}_{k_m}^m \right). \end{aligned}$$

This expression is useful for missing data for filling values in unknown cells in an incomplete data tensor or also for running a cross-validation in model selection for instance.

Reconstruction of reductions

When $\hat{\mathbf{C}}^\ell = (\hat{c}_{i_\ell k_\ell})_{i_\ell k_\ell} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell \times g_\ell}$ is the matrix aggregating the final posterior probabilities, the reduction of the matrix $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ induces also a reduction for each mode of the data tensor, with:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{\text{WLBM}}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \hat{\mathbf{C}}^\ell \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^\ell.$$

Let denote n_0 and r_0 the average values of n_ℓ and r_ℓ in Table 6 where is recalled the number of parameters to be estimated with the re-parameterized WLBm for factorization, the sizes of the latent variables are dramatically reduced in comparison with a full decomposition of the data tensor \mathbf{x} without clustering. Say for each mode ℓ , $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{g_\ell \times r_\ell}$ instead of $\boldsymbol{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell \times r_\ell}$ previously, while the ranks of the involved tensors w.r.t. r_ℓ must be discussed. Moreover, for big tensors, the matrices \hat{c}^ℓ may be kept sparse by preferring the maximum a posteriori for hard clustering with binary values instead of soft clustering with probability values.

Direct alternative

One may prefer to focus on the clustering from WLBm without the proposed parameterization via latent vectors. Hence, it may be performed a decomposition $\tilde{\Lambda}, \tilde{\xi}_{k_1}, \dots, \tilde{\xi}_{k_m}$ only after the inference of the co-clustering model from the final estimates $\tilde{\alpha}_{k_1 \dots k_m}$. This alternative approach may be written:

$$\phi^{-1}(\tilde{\alpha}_{k_1, \dots, k_m}) \approx \tilde{\Lambda} \oplus_s \tilde{\xi}_{k_1}^1 \oplus_s \dots \oplus_s \tilde{\xi}_{k_m}^m.$$

Note that the purpose may be $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{\text{WLBm}}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)} \approx \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)}$ but the dimensions of the tensor $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{k_1}^m$ are dramatically smaller than the clustered observed tensor \mathbf{x} . Hence the obtained reduction $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{\text{WLBm}}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)}$ may be of smaller dimensions than $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{\mathbf{x}(\ell)}$ and a quantization required by increasing g_ℓ . But including the decomposition within the model offers different and eventually better modeling for data analysis. This may happen for varying variances among blocks or overlapping with fuzzy reconstructions.

4.3 Related models and methods

The objective function of WLBm for Poisson data is related to a χ^2 criterion also found in correspondence analysis (CA) [51, 52, 26], such that the two methods share several similarities, see [53] when the latent factors for the rows and columns are clustered. Moreover, CA was extended to tensor tables by several authors, see Multiway correspondence Analysis (MCA) [54, 55] or Multiple Factor Analysis [56] for instance. For Gaussian data, there are several alternative methods to WLBm which are also often related and which lead to computed latent factors as herein. They are for recall: Classical Tucker decomposition (TK-D), Orthogonal Tucker decomposition (OTK-D via HOOI), High Order Singular Value Decomposition (HOSVD via ALS+SVD). More recently, for CA/PCA reduction of data tensors, some methods are: Matricization for one mode followed by PCA, Multiway/Multilinear PCA or SVD. The key difference herein is the clustering of the rows and the columns with less parameters as presented next subsection with full tensorial expressions of the objective functions.

5 Implementations for $W_3\text{LBM}+(\text{CP}/\text{TK})\text{-D}$

Above, it has been proposed a general framework for latent block model and tensors. First the problem is rewritten in a full tensorial notation. Let define $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times J \times K}$ the data tensor, and for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$, the weight matrices from cluster membership $C^\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell \times g_\ell}$, and the latent factors $\xi^\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{g_\ell \times r_\ell}$ while $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{R_1 \times R_2 \times R_3}$ denotes the Tucker *core* and $\theta = (\Lambda, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3)$. The variance $\sigma_{k_1}^2$ are supposed fixed.

5.1 Clustering in the Gaussian model

The objective function to optimize for the decomposition is written as follows once the posterior probabilities $C = (C^1, C^2, C^3)$ were obtained at previous step,

$$\begin{aligned} Q_G^{(3)}(\theta|C) &= \sum_{I_3, \mathcal{K}_3} \prod_{o=1}^3 c_{i_o k_o}^o (x_{i_1}^3 - \alpha_k^m)^2 \\ &= \langle \alpha \odot \alpha, C_\circ \rangle_F - 2 \langle \alpha, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_C \rangle_F + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_C\|_F^2 \\ &= \left\| C_\circ^{\frac{1}{2}} \odot \alpha - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_C \odot C_\circ \right\|_F^2 + \Phi_G. \end{aligned}$$

Here it is defined $\Phi_G = \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 - \|C_\circ^{-\frac{1}{2}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{x}}_C\|_F^2$, $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_C = \mathbf{x} \times_1 C^{1T} \times_2 C^{2T} \times_3 C^{3T}$, $C_\circ = c^{(1)} \circ c^{(2)} \circ c^{(3)}$, $c^{(\ell)} = C^{\ell T} \mathbf{1}_{n_\ell}$, while \odot denotes the term-wise Hadamard product, C_\circ the corresponding term-wise division and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_F$ is the Frobenius inner product. A reduced version with a small tensor to be factorized instead. The objective function is rewritten in tensorial form with two versions with different properties. More generally for Bernoulli, Gaussian, and Poisson distribution, the objective function may be also rewritten as a weighted Frobenius norm, see the appendix for the exact expression.

-0.23	1.60	1.70	-0.28	1.57	1.52	-0.14	-0.19	1.60	1.70	1.52	1.57	-0.28	-0.23	-0.14	-0.19
-1.62	2.94	2.92	-1.72	2.94	2.96	-1.57	-1.67	1.62	1.50	1.60	1.63	-0.28	-0.23	-0.21	-0.26
0.44	-1.55	-1.58	0.51	-1.53	-1.52	0.43	0.50	1.51	1.56	1.54	1.60	-0.28	-0.31	-0.13	-0.10
-1.65	2.90	2.79	-1.54	2.82	2.95	-1.58	-1.67	1.55	1.61	1.63	1.63	-0.16	-0.05	-0.19	-0.16
0.46	-1.66	-1.56	0.50	-1.50	-1.61	0.47	0.45	1.70	1.61	1.65	1.61	-0.23	-0.17	-0.31	-0.25
0.53	-1.65	-1.55	0.54	-1.60	-1.61	0.36	0.49	2.79	2.82	2.84	2.86	-1.50	-1.73	-1.53	-1.68
-1.73	2.79	2.82	-1.50	2.86	2.84	-1.53	-1.68	2.90	2.79	2.95	2.82	-1.54	-1.65	-1.58	-1.67
-0.23	1.62	1.50	-0.28	1.63	1.60	-0.21	-0.26	2.94	2.92	2.96	2.94	-1.72	-1.62	-1.57	-1.67
-0.05	1.55	1.61	-0.16	1.63	1.63	-0.19	-0.16	2.81	2.96	2.82	2.85	-1.50	-1.66	-1.58	-1.69
-0.31	1.51	1.56	-0.28	1.60	1.54	-0.13	-0.10	-1.66	-1.56	-1.61	-1.50	0.50	0.46	0.47	0.45
-0.17	1.70	1.61	-0.23	1.61	1.65	-0.31	-0.25	-1.55	-1.58	-1.52	-1.53	0.51	0.44	0.43	0.50
-1.66	2.81	2.96	-1.50	2.85	2.82	-1.58	-1.69	-1.65	-1.55	-1.61	-1.60	0.54	0.53	0.36	0.49

Table 7: Small matrices before (left) and after (right) ordering.

5.2 Decomposition in the Gaussian model

Let rewrite the criteria to optimize with the means as multilinear expressions of the latent factors. A semi-nmf related version for hard clusters with binarized clustering matrices C_{01} and the data tensor involved, is obtained for the non fuzzy criterion to optimize.

Proposition 1. *For the criterion of the cluterized Tucker decomposition with binarize posterior probabilities, the objective function for $W_3\text{LBM}$ when $\sigma_{k_1}^2$ are all equal may be rewritten:*

$$Q_G^{(3)}(\theta|C_{01}) = \left\| \mathbf{x} - \Lambda \times_1 \tilde{\xi}^{x(1)} \times_2 \tilde{\xi}^{x(2)} \times_3 \tilde{\xi}^{x(3)} \right\|_F^2 + \Phi_G.$$

Here it is defined for $\ell = 1, 2, 3$ the projected factors $\tilde{\xi}^\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell \times r_\ell}$ as follows: $\tilde{\xi}^{x(\ell)} = C^\ell \xi^\ell$ where $\xi^\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{g_\ell \times r_\ell}$ is the reduced view. The same expression holds when $\Lambda = \Lambda_r$ is diagonal for the criterion of the cluterized Canonical Polyadic decomposition with not fuzzy probabilities.

In this result, it is recognized an usual tensor decomposition for $m \geq 3$ or singular values decomposition for $m = 2$. Thus once the matrices $\hat{\Lambda}$ and $\hat{\xi}^{x^{(\ell)}}$ are computed from the tensor \mathbf{x} , the matrices $\hat{\xi}^\ell$ may be computed by clustering the fitted vectors $\hat{\xi}^{x^{(\ell)}}$. When one denotes $\mathbf{x}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ the decomposition with parameters $\Lambda \xi^{x^{(\ell)}}$ and similarly $\mathbf{x}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ with parameters $\tilde{\Lambda} \tilde{\xi}^{x^{(\ell)}}$, this may be justified by the following induced result.

Corollary 1. *Let denote constants $C_{\xi, \ell}$ and C_G , the Lipschitz property of the Tucker decomposition may lead to:*

$$\|\mathbf{x}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathbf{x}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})\|_F \leq C_\Lambda \|\Lambda - \tilde{\Lambda}\|_F + \sum_{\ell=1}^3 C_{\xi, \ell} \|\xi^{x^{(\ell)}} - \tilde{\xi}^{x^{(\ell)}}\|_F.$$

When the latent factors are obtained by exact clustering, the related norms vanish. The same happens for the norm of the core when uniqueness is achieved between the two decompositions but this is not to be expected because the factors are different. This induces the following notice.

Remark 1: *By minimizing an upper bound, a Tucker Decomposition followed by a clustering of the factors is related to the estimation of the parameters of G-W_mLBM when the matrices C^ℓ for the posterior probabilities are denoted binary $Z^\ell \in \{0, 1\}^{n_\ell \times g_\ell}$ and for common variances parameters $\sigma_{k_3} = \sigma$ all equal.*

Remark 2: *For two modes only ($m = 2$) this leads to compare the approximation from the proposed model when Λ diagonal and the usual decomposition from singular value decomposition (SVD) to,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} &\doteq Z^1 \xi^1 \Lambda \xi^{2T} Z^{2T} && \text{from } W_2\text{LBM} \\ \mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{U}_x \Sigma_x \mathbf{V}_x^T && \text{from SVD} \end{aligned}$$

The equality suggests to identify the optimal solution as follows,

$$\xi^1 \doteq C^{1T} \mathbf{U}_x \text{ and } \xi^2 \doteq C^{2T} \mathbf{V}_x.$$

A justification may be as follows in a more general case, with weights. Let denote $\sigma_{k_1 k_2}^2 = \sigma_{k_1}^2 \sigma_{k_2}^2$, $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_F$ for the Frobenius norm and $\|\cdot\|_2$ the spectral norm, then one may write that:

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(2)}(\boldsymbol{\theta} | C_{01}) &= \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}\|_F^2 \\ &= \|\mathbf{x} - Z^1 D_\sigma^1 \boldsymbol{\alpha} D_\sigma^2 Z^{2T}\|_F^2 \\ &\leq \|\xi^{x^{(1)}} - \tilde{\xi}^1\|_F \|\Sigma_x\|_2 + C_{\tilde{\xi}^1} \left(\|\Sigma_x - \Sigma_\alpha\|_F + \|\Sigma_\alpha\|_2 \|\xi^{x^{(2)}} - \tilde{\xi}^2\|_F \right). \end{aligned}$$

For this result, the main hypothesis is that the rank of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is equal or greater than the one of \mathbf{x} , hence, the noise from the data matrix has been removed, otherwise the norm for the noise is added to the upper bound. This looks like more likely true for large dimensional space. But also may induce that this bound has not always zero possible for minimum, with in particular $\Sigma_x \neq \Sigma_\alpha$ which is not always cancelled out when the vectors ξ^ℓ are not defined as orthonormal. Here, it is denoted $\tilde{\xi}^\ell = Z^\ell D_\sigma^\ell \xi_\alpha^\ell$ where $D^\ell = \text{Diag}(\sigma_{k_\ell}^{-1})$, while $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \xi_\alpha^1 \Sigma_\alpha \xi_\alpha^{2T}$ is a singular values decomposition (SVD) [57] and $C_{\tilde{\xi}^\ell}$ a upper bound for $\|\tilde{\xi}^\ell\|_2$. A probabilistic reverse inequality may be obtained with an usual concentration bound from Gaussian hypothesis of the noises as a perspective. Note also that the weights are naturally estimated from the gaussian model as related to variance terms with the criterion: $-0.5 Q^{(2)}(\boldsymbol{\theta} | C) - \sum_{k_1 k_2} c_{k_1}^1 c_{k_2}^2 \log(\sigma_{k_1} \sigma_{k_2})$. This may induce that the log-likelihood of a latent block model with outer products from vectors for the variance parameters is upper bounded by a criterion for clustering separately the latent factors from a decomposition of the data tensor, with also varying variance terms in the clusters.

Illustration: *In this example, it is checked the equality between the singular decomposition and latent block model for gaussian data with common variance parameters and Z^ℓ binary classification matrices with corresponding posterior probabilities matrices C^ℓ . The generated matrix and reordored matrix according to the label are given in Table 7, with heatmap in Figure 3. The matrix for the centers are a follows:*

$$N_\alpha = \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 31.94 & -4.16 \\ \hline 45.97 & -25.89 \\ \hline -18.92 & 5.68 \\ \hline \end{array} \quad D_\alpha = \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 20 & 20 \\ \hline 16 & 16 \\ \hline 12 & 12 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Figure 3: Small matrices before (left) and after (right) ordering.

Let denote $N_\alpha = Z^T \mathbf{x} Z^2$ and $D_\alpha = Z^T \mathbf{1}_{n_1 n_2} Z^2$, and $\mathbf{1}_{n_1 n_2}$ is for the matrix of ones of size $n_1 \times n_2$ while $\xi^1 = C^T U_x$ and $\xi^2 = C^2 V_x$ with $C^\ell = \text{Diag}(\mathbf{x} \mathbf{1}_{n_2})^{-1} Z^\ell$. According to the identification above, this may lead to the equality:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = N_\alpha \odot D_\alpha = C^T \mathbf{x} C^2 = \xi^1 \Sigma_x \xi^{2T}.$$

Finally, when the clustering is binary, one may get the approximation for the data matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = Z^1 \boldsymbol{\alpha} Z^{2T} = Z^1 \xi^1 \Sigma_x \xi^{2T} Z^{2T}$. For this data matrix with small noises, this leads to $Q^{(2)}(\boldsymbol{\theta} | C_{01})$ identical to the value obtained from the sum of squares w.r.t. i_ℓ and k_ℓ from the former non matricial expression.

Remark 3: It is recognized clustering criteria from K-means such that the latent factors ξ^ℓ in the model are cluster centers from the former singular vectors from the SVD. Such method was proposed in [58] while being retrieved and generalized [59] to tensors herein. The identity above was not proposed before to our knowledge because comparisons have focused on matricial methods, while herein a model based method is related too. See also TBM [50] for another related clustering method without noise modeling. This result is also obtained for $m > 2$ because of the unicity of the solution of the SVD as for TK-D under orthonormality constraints and relevant rotations: $\hat{\xi}^\ell \doteq C^{\ell T} \hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}^{(\ell)}}$ for all ℓ . The solution for the model with hard binary posterior probabilities may be obtained by clustering the decomposition of the data tensor.

But this solution requires the estimation of large matrices $\hat{\xi}^{\mathbf{x}^{(\ell)}}$ and relevant factors ranks, this is avoided by a direct tensor clustering.

Extended criterion In most of the cases including Bernoulli and Poisson ones, once the reduced expression is obtained, a related result may be obtained.

Proposition 2. Let denote \mathbf{z}_x for one value among $\mathbf{z}_G = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_C \odot C_\circ$, \mathbf{z}_B or \mathbf{z}_{NB} while Φ is a remaining constant term. The objective function for W_3LBM may be written as follows:

$$Q^{(3)}(\boldsymbol{\theta} | C) = \|C_\circ^{\frac{1}{2}} \odot (\mathbf{z}_x - \Lambda \times_1 \check{\xi}^1 \times_2 \check{\xi}^2 \times_3 \check{\xi}^3)\|_F^2 + \Phi.$$

Here it is defined $\check{\xi}^\ell = D_{(\ell)}^{\frac{1}{2}} \xi^\ell$ with $D_{(\ell)} = \text{diag}(c^{(\ell)})$.

This allows directly to use the model for computing the decomposition from a small matrix \mathbf{z}_x instead of the tensor \mathbf{x} which is bigger.

Remark 4: For a covariance matrix $\Sigma = (\sigma_{k_1^3})$, an usual Weights ALS is required. The following Table summaries several variants for the multiway gaussian latent block model.

Definition	Σ	$\boldsymbol{\alpha}$
All different	$(\sigma_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$
All common	$(\sigma_{k_1^3} = \sigma)$	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$
Mode ℓ common	$(\sigma_{k_1^3} = \sigma_{k_\ell})$	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$
Outer inverse	$(\sigma_1 \circ \sigma_2 \circ \sigma_3)^{-1}$	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$
Lasso sparse	$\min_{\Sigma} Q_G(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \Sigma) + \lambda_{\Sigma} \Sigma $	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$
CP ϵ_{Σ} -sparse	$\sum_s \lambda_s \sigma_{1s} \circ \sigma_{2s} \circ \sigma_{3s}, \lambda_s > 1 - \epsilon_{\Sigma}$	$(\alpha_{k_1^3})_{k_1^3}$

Table 8: Family of variants for G- W_3LBM with constraints.

This underlines the flexibility of the model which can support many constraints without breaking. Note diagonal ways for α has already demonstrated the relevance of constraints. Unfortunately, the case of the covariance matrix has known less work in the literature while lasso was also shown successful in TBM [50] at improving the tensor clustering.

Next, algorithms for fitting the latent factors during or after the clustering are discussed.

5.3 Implemented algorithms for WLBM

As an approximation, it may be approximated the clustering from the latent factors on the data tensor of by a direct decomposition on the reduced tensor with the $\alpha_{k_1 k_2 k_3}^{(t+1)}$, at least if the variances are all equal. Otherwise a numerical procedure for nonlinear optimization of the proposed criterion is required such that the direct decomposition becomes a possible initialization before the algorithm itself: see Algorithm 3 and Algorithm 2 near below.

Algorithm 1: VEM-W₃LBM($\mathbf{x}, g_1, g_2, g_3$)

Input: $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2 \times n_3}$, $g_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $g_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, $g_3 \in \mathbb{R}$

Output: θ , C^1 , C^1 , C^1

for $t \leftarrow 1$ **to** $t_{max} - 1$ **do**

- Update of posterior probabilities C^ℓ

for $t^{in} \leftarrow 1$ **to** $iter_{max}^{in}$ **do**

$$c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t; t^{in}+1)} \propto p_{\ell k_\ell}^{(t)} e^{\left(\sum_{I_m \setminus \{i_\ell, k_m\} \setminus k_\ell} \left[\prod_{o \neq \ell} c_{i_\ell k_o}^{o(t; t^{in})} \right] \log \varphi(x_{i_\ell}^m; \theta_{k_\ell}^{(t)}) \right)}$$

$$c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t+1)} = c_{i_\ell k_\ell}^{\ell(t; t_{max}^{in})}$$

- Update of distribution parameters θ

$$\theta^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax} \tilde{Q}_{W_m LBM}(\theta, \theta^{(t)})$$

return $\hat{\theta}$, \hat{C}^1 , \hat{C}^1 , \hat{C}^1

Algorithm 2: DualMatrixRidgeRegression($A, B, C, \lambda_X, \lambda_B$)

Input: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times q}$, $\lambda_X \geq 0$, $\lambda_B \geq 0$

Output: $f(X^*)$, $\nabla f(X^*)$, X^*

$$R \leftarrow BB^T + \lambda_B I_p$$

$$L \leftarrow A^T A + \lambda_X I_n$$

$$X^* \leftarrow L^{-1} A^T C B^T R^{-1}$$

$$f(X^*) \leftarrow \|AX^*B - C\|_F^2 + \lambda_X \|X^*\|_F^2$$

$$\nabla f(X^*) \leftarrow 2(A^T A X^* R + \lambda_X X^* - A^T C B^T)$$

return $f(X^*)$, $\nabla f(X^*)$, X^*

Here, a weighted ALS with a particular structure of the weights for tensor is implemented directly thanks to the properties of the Hadamard product which allows to distribute the outer product into products with diagonal matrices. Each step is a Ridge Matrix Regression for solving the least-squares problem. An orthogonalisation is also introduced after optimisation for an approximation as in HOOI for instance, a more exact approach is left as a perspective. For (non binarized) posteriors probabilities, the second version of the objective function allows to decompose a small tensor \mathbf{z} instead of the former data one \mathbf{x} . The Alternating Least Squares is with diagonal weighted because of the matrix C_o , see the algorithm 3. The notations are as follows: \times_n for tensor product with a matrix along mode n , $X_{(n)}$ for tensor *unfolding* along mode n , and \otimes for Kronecker product. Experiments must validate this parameterization in order to check the convergence of the algorithms and the final quality of the eventual resulting reductions. These algorithms suggest several approaches for tensor decomposition which need to be adressed and compared.

Algorithm 3: OuterWeightedALS($\mathbf{x}, c^{(1)}, c^{(2)}, c^{(3)}, r_1, r_2, r_3$).

Input: $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2 \times n_3}$, $c^{(\ell)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell}$, (r_1, r_2, r_3) ranks

Output: $\Lambda, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3$

Initialize ξ^1, ξ^2, ξ^3 (e.g. HOSVD or randomly)

Denote $D^{(\ell)} = \text{diag}(c^{(\ell)})$ and $\check{\xi}^\ell = D^{(\ell)\frac{1}{2}} \xi^\ell$ for all ℓ

for $iter \leftarrow 1$ **to** $iter_{max}$ **do**

- Update of $\Lambda = fold_1(\Lambda_{(1)})$
 $\Lambda_1 \leftarrow \arg \min_{\Lambda_1} \|\mathbf{x}_{(1)} - \check{\xi}^1(\Lambda_{(1)}(\check{\xi}^3 \otimes \check{\xi}^2)^T)\|_F^2$
- Update of ξ^1
 $\xi^1 \leftarrow \arg \min_{U_1} \|\mathbf{x}_{(1)} - \check{\xi}^1(\Lambda_{(1)}(\check{\xi}^3 \otimes \check{\xi}^2)^T)\|_F^2$
 $\xi^1 \leftarrow \text{QR}(\xi^1)$
- Update of ξ^2
 $\xi^2 \leftarrow \arg \min_{U_2} \|\mathbf{x}_{(2)} - \check{\xi}^2(\Lambda_{(2)}(\check{\xi}^3 \otimes \check{\xi}^1)^T)\|_F^2$
 $\xi^2 \leftarrow \text{QR}(\xi^2)$
- Update of ξ^3
 $\xi^3 \leftarrow \arg \min_{U_3} \|\mathbf{x}_{(3)} - \check{\xi}^3(\Lambda_{(3)}(\check{\xi}^2 \otimes \check{\xi}^1)^T)\|_F^2$
 $\xi^3 \leftarrow \text{QR}(\xi^3)$

Return $\Lambda, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3$

6 Numerical experiments

In this section, the proposed multiway latent block model and its parameterization are illustrated and validated with real data for a reduction associated to a co-clustering by comparing to current state of art. If preliminary work has tested correspondence analysis for tensorization of textual contingency tables, the approach was successful only for non overlapping clusters, hence this is images dataset with usual tensorization into cube which are involved next. The two subsection presents the results for clustering first and for the decomposition after in order to compare with the classical usual Tucker decomposition found in the literature. The code for the model and the experiments may be available at the url² at Github or PyPI or by author emailing.

Three datasets are considered for the experiments as they are usual benchmark data. Table 9 summarizes the sizes and number of classes.

	(n_1, n_2, n_3)	g	(r_1, r_2, r_3)	(g_1, g_2, g_3)
YALE32	(165, 32, 32)	15	(15, 15, 15)	(15, 10, 10)
YALE64	(165, 64, 64)	15	(15, 15, 15)	(15, 10, 10)
COIL20	(1440, 32, 32)	20	(20, 20, 20)	(20, 10, 10)

Table 9: Tensor size, classes number, Tucker ranks and cluster numbers.

This is data tensors with images of size 32×32 or 64×64 which are aggregated as a three dimensional form with one dimension for the images and the other dimensions for the width and height. An example of images are below in Figure 4 such that one same object or face are repeated with transformation, a rotation or an expression change.

A min+max normalisation was performed by subtracting the minimum of each slice and dividing by the maximum minus the minimum. The clustering must compare the estimated label with the true classes. To evaluate the model, the algorithm and its current implementations for clustering, it is computed the normalized mutual information score (nmi).

The obtained Table 10 suggests that the proposed method is able to lead to acceptable values when well initialized for several datasets. Here the initialization is with two different methods for comparison, the clustered Tucker decomposition (denoted $TK - D + KM$) and the method (denoted C_{co}^{123} with here 50 trials as for KM) proposed at the review section in Figure 1 both in Python language as the other methods herein. The implementations for WLBM are denoted $G-W_3LBM(\sigma, C_{01})$ with common variances and hard

²<https://github.com/rpriam/multilbm-code>

Figure 4: Images from COIL20 32×32 .

Method	Algo	Init	NMI			ARI		
			Yale32	Yale64	COIL20	Yale32	Yale64	COIL20
TK-D+KM	ALS	SVD	0.56±05	0.65±04	0.74±02	0.26±06	0.38±05	0.53±03
C_{co}^{123}		RANDOM	0.58±03	0.60±03	0.69±03	0.30±05	0.33±05	0.43±04
G-W ₃ LBM(σ, C_{01})	VEM*	C_{co}^{123}	0.59±03	0.63±04	0.74±03	0.31±05	0.36±06	0.50±05
G-W ₃ LBM($\sigma_{k_1^3}, C$)	VEM*	C_{co}^{123}	0.60±03	0.63±04	0.69±03	0.32±05	0.36±05	0.43±04
G-W ₃ LBM(σ, C_{01})	VEM*	TK-D + KM	0.58±04	0.66±03	0.76±02	0.29±06	0.40±05	0.56±04
G-W ₃ LBM($\sigma_{k_1^3}, C$)	VEM*	TK-D + KM	0.58±04	0.66±04	0.73±02	0.28±05	0.39±06	0.51±03

Table 10: NMI and ARI from several methods or initializations and four images datasets for 35 bootstrap samples.

binary $c_{ik\ell}^\ell$ and G-W₃LBM(σ, C_{01}) with different variances and fuzzy $c_{ik\ell}^\ell$, when both initialized from C_{co}^{123} . The implementation for WLBM have similar constraints on the parameters but initialized by *TK-D+KM* with respective denotations G-W₃LBM(σ, C_{01}) and G-W₃LBM($\sigma_{k_1^3}, C$). The experiments confirms that the method if often near the results from TK-D. Some variabilities and differences for the scores may come from outliers, noises and non exact gaussianity while the inference algorithms are also different too. In future, the implemented algorithm -here *VEM** for the described algorithm in the previous sections- may be improved by tuning more the parameters and the smoothing constants, by selection after several trial runs and by preferring more robust estimators.

7 Discussion and perspectives

This document presents a multiway generative model suitable for co-clustering and reduction of tensor data in a full probabilistic setting by a parameterization of a new extended latent block model, named WLBM. The need for a clustering along all the modes comes from the resulting quantization which partitions each mode in order to reduce its size accordingly into a low dimensional space. Parameterization of latent block model is very powerfull, as it is able to lead to visualization of large datasets while also able to help for a generic sparse model by selection of the blocks to have common distributions. The proposed model herein is related to classical tensor analysis in order to extend latent variables models for matrices with more generality. The main contributions are: a) Multiway block latent model (WLBM) for a tensor, b) Parameterization of WLBM for factorization or PCA of tensor, c) Parameterization of WLBM for a generic sparse model, d) Implementation of WLBM for gaussian or bernoullian or poissonian cells, e) Experiments with new models with tensors and tensorized matrices for comparison with state of art and with correspondence analysis. Perspectives may be alternative reductions or decompositions such that block-term one [60] for optimal results, and a further analysis of the tensorization with WLBM for deep CA [61] and deep co-clustering [62], with automatic selection of the best model. To finish, numerical experiments with binary and count data will ask for non negative and sequential algorithms in future implementations.

Appendix: Bounds for (B/P)W₃LBM

Non Gaussian model are also available by optimizing a bound of the criterion such as found in [63, 64] for binary regression models. This is written here as follows. For the Bernoulli case, a bound from a previous value $\theta^{(t)}$ in the vicinity of the optimized parameters is directly available from the literature of the logit model

and summing, with $\alpha_{k_1^3} = \sigma(\tau_{k_1^3})$ a sigmoid and:

$$Q_B(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}, C) \geq -\frac{1}{8} \|C_o^{\frac{1}{2}} \odot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}_B)\|_F^2 + \Phi_B.$$

Here, $\mathbf{z}_B = (z_{k_1^3, B})$ when denoting $z_{k_1^3, B} = \tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)} + 4(x_{k_1^3}^{(t)}/c_{k_1^3} - \sigma(\tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)}))$, while $\Phi_B = \sum_{\mathcal{X}_3} (-C_o^{k_1^3} \cdot \log(1 + e^{u_{k_1^3}^{(t)}}) + \frac{C_o^{k_1^3}}{8} \tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)2})$.

For the Poisson case, a Negative Binomial is preferred by taking the related variance term $\varepsilon_{k_1^3}$ small. This makes appear also a related logit term such that:

$$Q_{NB}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(t)}, C) \geq -\frac{1}{8} \|C_o^{\frac{1}{2}} \odot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}_{NB})\|_F^2 + \Phi_{NB}.$$

Here $\mathbf{z}_{NB} = (z_{k_1^3, NB})$ with $z_{k_1^3, NB} = \log \varepsilon_{k_1^3} + \tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)} + 4(x_{k_1^3}^{(t)}/\gamma_{k_1^3} - \sigma(\tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)}))$, while $\gamma_{k_1^3} = x_{k_1^3}^{(t)} + \varepsilon_{k_1^3} C_o^{k_1^3}$, $\Phi_{NB} = \sum_{\mathcal{X}_3} [-(x_{k_1^3}^{(t)} + \varepsilon_{k_1^3}) \log(1 + e^{\tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)} - \log \varepsilon_{k_1^3}}) + \frac{\gamma_{k_1^3}}{8} \cdot \tau_{k_1^3}^{(t)2}]$, This recalls the classical IRLS updates in regression, but here for multi-modes tensor decomposition with latent Tucker factors.

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